

On Quantum BCH Codes and Its Duals

J. S. Bhullar and Manish Gupta

Abstract—Classical Bose-Chaudhuri-Hocquenghem (BCH) codes C that contain their dual codes can be used to construct quantum stabilizer codes this chapter studies the properties of such codes. It had been shown that a BCH code of length n which contains its dual code satisfies the bound on weight of any non-zero codeword in C^\perp and converse is also true. One impressive difficulty in quantum communication and computation is to protect information-carrying quantum states against undesired interactions with the environment. To address this difficulty, many good quantum error-correcting codes have been derived as binary stabilizer codes. We were able to shed more light on the structure of dual containing BCH codes. These results make it possible to determine the parameters of quantum BCH codes in terms of weight of non-zero dual codeword.

Keywords—Quantum Codes, BCH Codes, Dual BCH Codes, Designed Distance.

I. INTRODUCTION

QUANTUM Error Correction is one of the basic components of quantum information theory. Quantum information processing can be used to solve problems in cryptography, secure communication and physics simulation exponentially faster than any of its possible classical analogues. Quantum computers physical models allow exact realizations of quantum information and its manipulation, provided the underlying assumptions are satisfied. However, it is unrealistic to assume that the practical physical systems will behave like the ideal models. Quantum data is very vulnerable to decoherence, interaction with the environment which is due to incomplete isolation of the system from the rest of the world. Also, control errors, which are caused by calibration errors and fluctuations in control parameters, have to be taken care of. Some kind of error correction is necessary to reduce the effects of these errors. Soon after the existence of quantum error correction was proved in the pioneering paper by Shor [1], the first constructions of good quantum error-correcting codes were given by Steane [2] and Calderbank and Shor [3]. These codes protect the quantum information using additional qubits (A qubit is a unit vector in a two dimensional complex vector space for which a particular basis, denoted by $|0\rangle$, $|1\rangle$, has been fixed.) and make it possible to reverse the effects of the most likely errors.

Encouraged by these positive results, researchers investigated and constructed many new quantum error correcting codes. The fault-tolerant implementations of several

quantum operations were also discovered. These implementations make the basic assumption that the effects of all errors are sufficiently small per quantum bit and step of the computation.

Quantum information theory is rapidly becoming a well-established discipline. It shares many of the concepts of classical information theory but involves new subtleties arising from the nature of quantum mechanics. Among the central concepts in common between classical and quantum information is that of error correction. Quantum error-correcting codes have progressed from their initial discovery [1] to broader analyses of the physical principles [5]-[8] and various code constructions [8], [12], [19].

The first quantum error correcting codes were discovered independently by Shor [1] and Steane [2]. Shor proved that 9 qubits could be used to protect a single qubit against general errors, while Steane described a general code construction whose simplest example does the same job using 7 qubits. A general theory of quantum error correction dates from subsequent papers of Calderbank and Shor [3] and Steane [4] in which general code constructions, existence proofs, and correction methods were given. Knill and Laflamme [5] and Bennett et al. [6] provided a more general theoretical framework, describing requirements for quantum error correcting codes, and measures of the fidelity of corrected states. The important concept of the stabilizer is due to Gottesman [7] and independently Calderbank et al. [8]; this found many useful insights into the subject, and permitted many new codes to be discovered [7]-[9]. Stabilizer methods will probably make a valuable contribution to other areas in quantum information physics. The idea of recursively encoding and encoding again was explored by several authors [10]-[12], using quantum resources in a hierarchical way, to permit communication over arbitrarily long times or distances. Building upon the ideas of quantum error correction, fault-tolerant quantum computation was first proposed by Shor [13]. These ideas were summarized by Preskill [14]. Gottesman put forward a significant number of further ideas on fault-tolerant quantum computing [15], which allow fault tolerant methods to be found for a wide class of Quantum error correction codes, and the methods were further improved in [16], [17].

II. PRINCIPLES OF ERROR CORRECTION OF QUANTUM CODES

Although quaternary constructions [18] yield good quantum codes, building quantum codes from binary was suggested by Calderbank and Shor [3] and Steane [4], [22]. Recently, Steane [9] proposed an enlargement of the Calderbank-Shor-Steane construction, leading to several families of codes with fixed minimum distance and growing length. Cohen et al. [23] further improved the estimates of code parameters obtained

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from Steane's construction, and presented examples of new codes, and analyze asymptotic non constructive bounds.

The minimum distance d of the quantum code C is the largest generalized weight of a vector in $C \setminus C^\perp$. This code has parameters $[[n, k, d]]$ where $k = \log_2 |C| - n$.

Let $C[n, k, d]$ denoted a binary linear code of length n , dimension k , and minimum distance d .

For a more description Quantum theory of codes see [20].

III. SOME NEW QUANTUM CODES

Steane [16] proved that the primitive BCH codes of length $2^m - 1$ contain their duals if and only if their designed distance $d = 2t + 1$ satisfies

$$d \leq 2^{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor} - 1$$

It following form [20] that in this case the codes have parameter

$$[2^m - 1, 2^m - 1 - mt, 2t + 1]$$

Moreover, these codes are nested, i.e. form a chain for the inclusive relation when t increases. Extending them with a parity bit, [23] derived the families of codes.

Calderbank in [18] shows how to construct an $[[n, k + 1, d - 1]]$ -code from an $[[n, K, d]]$ -code. Using it [23] constructed from F_0 the following family

$$F_5 [[2^m, 2^m - (5l + 3)m - 1 + b, 6l + 5]]$$

for $6l + 6 \leq 2^{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor}$

It is tempting to conjecture the existence of families of codes with parameters

$$F_a [[2^m, 2^m - (5l + a - 2)m + b, 6l + a]]$$

where $a = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ and b is a small integer constant. Cohen et al [20] also proved the following result:

Theorem 1 [23]: For $6l + 4 \leq 2^{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor}$ there exist quantum codes with parameters

$$F_4 [[2^m, 2^m - (5l + 2)m - 1, 6l + 4]]$$

Theorem 2 [16]: Let $C[n, k, d]$, $C^\perp \subseteq C$, be a classical binary linear error-correcting code with generator matrix G . Let C be a subcode of a code $C'[n, k' > k + 1, d']$ with generator matrix $\begin{pmatrix} G \\ G' \end{pmatrix}$, then

$$G = \begin{bmatrix} G & 0 \\ 0 & G \\ G' & PG' \end{bmatrix}$$

where P is an invertible fix-point free map generates a quantum code of parameters

$$[[n, k + k' - n, \geq \min \left(d, \left\lfloor \frac{3d'}{2} \right\rfloor \right)]]$$

Thangaraj and McLaughlin [28] used the ideas of Calderbank et al. [8] to construct a new class of quantum codes from cyclic over $GF(4^m)$. In particular, the following theorem from [8] can be used directly to obtain quantum codes from the certain codes from certain code over $GF(4)$.

Theorem 3 [22]: Suppose C is an (n, k) linear code over $GF(4)$ self-orthogonal with respect to the Hermitian inner product. Suppose also that the minimum weight $C^\perp \setminus C$ is d . Then an $[[n, n - 2k, d]]$ quantum code can be obtained from C

The Hermitian inner product of $u, v \in GF(4)^n$ is defined to be

$$u \cdot v = u_1 \bar{v}_1 + u_2 \bar{v}_2 + \dots + u_n \bar{v}_n$$

where $\bar{\omega} = \omega^2$ for $\omega \in GF(4)$.

Thangaraj and McLaughlin [28] considered self-orthogonal codes over $GF(4)$ that are obtained as 4-ary images of 4^m -ary cyclic codes of the length $n|(4^m - 1)$. Binary images of the self-orthogonal codes over $GF(2^m)$ have been used to obtain Quantum codes in [27].

IV. QUANTUM BCH CODES

Calderbank, Shor, Rains, and Sloane outlined the construction of binary quantum BCH codes in [8]. Grassl, Beth and Pellizari developed the theory further by formulating a nice condition for BCH codes [24], [25]. Steane simplified it further for the special case of binary narrow-sense primitive BCH codes [9] and gave a very simple criterion based on the design distance along. Very little was done with respect to the nonprimitive and nonbinary quantum BCH codes.

Aly et al [26] gave very simple conditions based on design distance alone. Further he gave precisely the dimension and tighten results on the purity of the quantum codes from classical codes

Theorem 4 [26] Let $m = \text{ord}_n(q) \geq 2$, where q is a power of a prime and δ_1, δ_2 are integers such that $2 \leq \delta_1 < \delta_2 \leq \delta_{\max}$ where

$$\delta_{\max} = \frac{n}{q^m - 1} \left(q^{\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor} - 1 - (q - 2)[m \text{ odd}] \right)$$

Then there exist a Quantum code with parameter

$$[[n, m \left(\delta_2 - \delta_1 - \left\lfloor \frac{\delta_2 - 1}{q} \right\rfloor + \left\lfloor \frac{\delta_1 - 1}{q} \right\rfloor \right)], \geq \delta_1]_q$$

pure to δ_2 .

When BCH codes contain their duals then following result is derived by [21]

Theorem 5 [26] Let $m = \text{ord}_n(q)$ where q is a power of a prime and $2 \leq \delta \leq \delta_{\max}$, with

$$\delta_{\max} = \frac{n}{q^m - 1} \left(q^{\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor} - 1 - (q - 2)[m \text{ odd}] \right),$$

Then there exists a quantum code with parameters

$$[[n, n - 2m[(\delta - 1)(1 - 1/q)], \geq \delta]]_q$$

pure to $\delta_{\max} + 1$

Theorem 6 [26] Let $m = \text{ord}_n(q^2) \geq 2$ where q is a power of a prime and $2 \leq \delta \leq \delta_{\max} = \lfloor n(q^m - 1)/(q^{2m} - 1) \rfloor$, then there exists a quantum code with parameters

$$[[n, n - 2m[(\delta - 1)(1 - 1/q^2)], \geq \delta]]_q$$

that is pure up to $\delta_{\max} + 1$

In the above theorem, quantum codes can also be constructed when the design distance exceeds the given value of δ_{\max} .

These are not the only possible families of quantum codes that can derived from BCH codes over F_{q^l} to get codes makes it very easy to specify such codes. Similar results can be derived for the Hermitian case.

Theorem 7 [26] Let $m = \text{ord}_n(q^l)$ where q is a power of a prime and $2 \leq \delta \leq \delta_{\max}$, with

$$\delta_{\max} = \frac{n}{q^{lm} - 1} \left(q^{\lfloor \frac{lm}{2} \rfloor} - 1 - (q^l - 2)[m \text{ odd}] \right)$$

Then there exists a quantum code with parameters

$$[[ln, ln - 2lm[(\delta - 1)(1 - 1/q^l)], \geq \delta]]_q$$

The Next theorem from [1] used mainly for the construction of the quantum BCH codes [24] describes a necessary and sufficient conditions for the self-orthogonality of the cyclic codes over GF(4).

Theorem 8 A linear cyclic codes over GF(4) of the length $n|(4^m - 1)$ and the generator of the polynomials $g(x)$ is self-orthogonal if any only if

$$g(x)g^\dagger(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{(x^n - 1)}$$

where if

$$g(x) = \sum_{r=0}^{n-1} g_r x^r$$

$$g^\dagger(x) = \text{GCD} \left(\bar{g}_0 + \sum_{r=0}^{n-1} \bar{g}_{n-r} x^r, x^n - 1 \right)$$

and $\bar{g}_i = g_i^2$.

Generator polynomials of cyclic codes of the length $n|(4^m - 1)$ over GF(4) are usually specified in the terms of their zeros in GF(4^m).

Lemma 1 [20] Suppose C is a binary BCH code of length $n = 2^m - 1$ with designed distance $\delta = 2t + 1$, where $2t - 1 \leq 2^{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor} + 1$, then the weight w of any non-zero codeword in C^\perp lies in the range

$$2^{m-1} - (t - 1)2^{m/2} \leq w \leq 2^{m-1} + (t - 1)2^{m/2}$$

Theorem 10 Let C be binary BCH code of length $n = 2^m - 1$ with designed distance $\delta = 2t + 1$, where

$$2t - 1 \leq 2^{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor} + 1$$

and w be the weight of any non-zero codeword in C^\perp , then $C^\perp \subset C$ if and only if weight w lies in the range of

$$\frac{(n - 3)^2}{16} - (t - 1) \frac{n - 5}{2} < w < (n - 5) \frac{t}{2}$$

Proof:

$$2^{m-1} - (t - 1)2^{m/2} \leq w \leq 2^{m-1} + (t - 1)2^{m/2}$$

$$-(t - 1)2^{m/2} \leq w - 2^{m-1} \leq (t - 1)2^{m/2}$$

$$|w - 2^{m-1}| \leq (t - 1)2^{m/2}$$

$$2t - 1 \leq 2^{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor} + 1$$

$$\delta - 2 \leq 2^{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor} + 1$$

$$\delta \leq 2^{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor} + 3 = \delta_{\max}$$

But from [26]

$$\delta \leq \delta_{\max} = \left\lfloor \frac{n + 1}{2} \right\rfloor$$

So

$$2^{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor} + 3 = \left\lfloor \frac{n + 1}{2} \right\rfloor$$

$$2 \cdot 2^{(m/2) - \lfloor m/2 \rfloor} = \frac{n + 1}{2} - \left\lfloor \frac{n + 1}{2} \right\rfloor - 3 \leq \frac{n + 1}{2} - 3$$

$$2^{m/2} < \frac{n - 5}{2}$$

Again

$$2 \cdot 2^{(m/2) - \lfloor m/2 \rfloor} = \frac{n + 1}{2} - \left\lfloor \frac{n + 1}{2} \right\rfloor - 3 \geq \frac{n + 1}{2} + 1 - 3$$

$$2^{(m/2)} > \frac{n - 3}{4}$$

$$\frac{(n - 3)^2}{16} - (t - 1) \frac{n - 5}{2} < 2^{m-1} - (t - 1)2^{m/2} \leq w$$

$$\leq 2^{m-1} + (t - 1)2^{m/2}$$

$$< \frac{n - 5}{2} + (t - 1) \frac{n - 5}{2}$$

$$\frac{(n - 3)^2}{16} - (t - 1) \frac{n - 5}{2} < w < (n - 5) \frac{t}{2}$$

V. CONCLUSION

A conclusion section is not required. Although a conclusion may review the main points of the paper, do not replicate the abstract as the conclusion. A conclusion might elaborate on the importance of the work or suggest applications and extensions.

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